

Research Article

Clinical and Laboratory Characteristics and effect of Smoking Cessation on WBC and platelet indices: a retrospective study

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to assess the values of mean platelet volume (MPV) in regular smokers and the effect of smoking cessation on WBC and MPV. The study included 46 regular smokers (mean age: 36.4 + 9.6 years). Smokers were chosen among those who had visited a smoking cessation outpatient clinic from August 2021 through March 2022. 40 out of 46 frequent smokers were successful in quitting. Platelet indices, including MPV, platelet count, platelet distribution width (PDW), and white blood cell (WBC) count, were assessed per months following smoking cessation in 40 subjects and compared to their baseline platelet indices. There were no statistically significant differences between the Smoker and control groups with respect to age, gender, BMI 19.2/20.9, SBP 132/129.9, DBP 79.6/78.3 and levels of glucose higher in smoker group (102.8 ± 10.3/96.3 ± 10.9), creatinine 0.91±0.11 / 0.8 ± 0.2, total cholesterol 186.2 ± 36.9/196.5 ± 21.3, triglyceride 147.7±78.2/150.3 ± 73.8, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol 111.6±39.2/123.8 ± 30.6, high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol 42.9±10.0/45.9 ± 9.6, WBC 5.99±7.2/5.62 ±6.50, haemoglobin 14.9±1.0/14.2±1.5, The MPV values were significantly higher in smokers than those of controls (8.02 ± 0.72/7.50 ± 0.32) and PDW 15.1±1.3/15.2±1.6. Platelet count was higher in the control group 225.6 ± 32.0 than Smoker group 191.9 ± 40.2 but the difference did not reach a statistically significant level. By emphasizing the connection between smoking, platelet activation, and cardiovascular diseases, can contribute to increasing the motivation for smokers to make the decision to quit and ultimately improve their overall health and well-being.

Keywords: mean platelet volume, WBC, smoking, platelet activation, and cardiovascular diseases.

Introduction

Smoking's harmful effects appear to be both local and systemic. Smoking is linked to an increased risk of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and lung cancer, as well as extrapulmonary illnesses such cardiovascular disease, diabetes mellitus, and bladder cancer. [1-5] Although all studies have observed a positive association between smoking and total white blood cell counts, there have been some conflicting results for the subpopulations.[6-8] Chronic smoking is a significant modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular illnesses [9]. It not only accelerates atherosclerosis but also causes endothelial dysfunction and hemostatic disorders [10-11]. Previous research has shown that persistent smoking induces platelet activation [11-17]. Mean platelet volume (MPV) is a possible indicator of platelet reactivity [18,19]. In comparison to smaller ones, larger platelets have more granules, aggregate more rapidly with collagen, have higher thromboxane A₂ level, and express more glycoprotein Ib and IIb/IIIa receptors [20-22]. Some studies have reported that smoking has no effect on MPV [14,23]. On the other hand, Kario et al have found increased MPV values in smokers [24]. Platelet indices are blood-based parameters reflecting the activation of platelets. According to studies, the levels and proportions of cells (e.g., leukocytes, neutrophils, thrombocytes) such as the complete blood count can be utilized as a marker in the identification of systemic inflammation, which is known to have a role in the etiology of many illnesses. The neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio (NLR) is a composite measure generated using absolute neutrophil and lymphocyte counts [25]. Platelet/lymphocyte ratio (PLR), which is the combination of both parameters, is seen as a mortality determinant in cardiovascular and lung diseases and some malignant diseases [26]. Mean platelet volume (MPV) is a potential marker of platelet activation and MPV levels are elevated in thromboembolic diseases [27]. Many studies have shown that MPV/lymphocyte ratio (MPVLR) is also a

negative inflammatory marker in cardiovascular diseases and some malignant diseases [28,29]. Platelets possess the L-arginine–nitric oxide (NO) pathway through constitutive NO synthase in humans [31, 32]. We have previously shown that long-term smoking impairs platelet-derived nitric oxide (PDNO) release [30], which acts as a negative feedback mechanism to inhibit not only platelet aggregation [33] but also recruitment after aggregation [34].

Methods: Study subjects. The study included 46 regular smokers (mean age: 36.4 + 9.6 years). Smokers were chosen among those who had visited a smoking cessation outpatient clinic from August 2021 through March 2022. An age-, gender- and body mass index–matched control group was composed of 25 healthy volunteers (mean age 37.6 +9.2 years). In this study, persons who smoked at least 10 cigarettes per day for at least 5 years were deemed smokers. Nonsmokers (control group) were people who had never smoked and had not been exposed to tobacco smoke in the environment. All individuals had monthly blood and urine cotinine assays to track their smoking status. The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee, and all patients gave their informed consent.

Biochemical measurements: Biochemical measures and platelet indicators were taken in 46 regular smokers and 25 control subjects. 40 out of 46 frequent smokers were successful in quitting. Platelet indices, including MPV, platelet count, platelet distribution width (PDW), and white blood cell (WBC) count, were assessed per months following smoking cessation in 40 subjects and compared to their baseline platelet indices. Blood samples were obtained at least 120 minutes after the last smoke at admission to avoid smoking's immediate effects on platelet function. Diabetes mellitus was defined as a fasting blood glucose level >126 mg/dL.

Exclusion criteria: In present study we excluded the patients having history of heart

disease, alcohol use, medication, pregnancy, diabetes mellitus, obesity, history of renal or liver disease psychiatric disorders.

Blood sampling recorded at the time of admission and at per month after smoking cessation. Glucose, creatinine, and lipid profiles were determined by standard methods. The MPV was assessed in a blood sample obtained in dry K2 (dipotassium) EDTA vacuum tubes. An automatic blood counter (Cell-Dyn 3700 [Abbott Diagnostics, Santa Clara, CA, USA]) was used for whole blood. MPV was measured within 30 minutes to prevent EDTA induced swelling. The expected values for MPV in our laboratory ranged from 6.9 to 10.8 fL.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed with the SPSS software version 12.0 for Windows. Continuous variables from the study groups were reported as mean \pm SD and categorical variables as percentages. To compare continuous variables, the Student's *t*-test or Mann-Whitney U test were used when appropriate. Paired samples *t*-test was employed to compare platelet indices before and after smoking cessation. Categorical variables were compared using the Chi-squared

test. Statistical significance was determined as a P value less than 0.05.

Results

Clinical features and Laboratory characteristics of the patients/smokers and the control group are shown in Table 1. There were no statistically significant differences between the Smoker and control groups with respect to age, gender, BMI 19.2/20.9, SBP 132/129.9, DBP 79.6/78.3 and levels of glucose higher in smoker group ($102.8 \pm 10.3/96.3 \pm 10.9$), creatinine $0.91 \pm 0.11 / 0.8 \pm 0.2$, total cholesterol $186.2 \pm 36.9/196.5 \pm 21.3$, triglyceride $147.7 \pm 78.2/150.3 \pm 73.8$, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol $111.6 \pm 39.2/123.8 \pm 30.6$, high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol $42.9 \pm 10.0/45.9 \pm 9.6$, WBC $5.99 \pm 7.2/5.62 \pm 6.50$, haemoglobin $14.9 \pm 1.0/14.2 \pm 1.5$, The MPV values were significantly higher in smokers than those of controls ($8.02 \pm 0.72/7.50 \pm 0.32$) and PDW $15.1 \pm 1.3/15.2 \pm 1.6$. Platelet count was higher in the control group 225.6 ± 32.0 than Smoker group 191.9 ± 40.2 but the difference did not reach a statistically significant level.

Table 1. Comparison of the Clinical and Laboratory Characteristics of the Smokers and Controls.

	Smoker (n=46)	Control (n=25)	P value
Age (years)	36.4 \pm 9.6	37.6 \pm 9.2	0.63
Sex (M/F)	46/0	25/0	0.62
BMI (kg/m ²)	19.2 \pm 6.4	20.9 \pm 6.4	0.42
SBP (mm Hg)	132.0 \pm 8.6	129.9 \pm 6.0	0.20
DBP (mm Hg)	79.6 \pm 6.7	78.3 \pm 6.3	0.10
Smoking (Year)	6.9 \pm 7.9		
Cigarettes per day	12.3 \pm 7.8		
Glucose (mg/dL)	102.8 \pm 10.3	96.3 \pm 10.9	0.21
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.91 \pm 0.11	0.8 \pm 0.2	0.16
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	186.2 \pm 36.9	196.5 \pm 21.3	0.10
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	147.7 \pm 78.2	150.3 \pm 73.8	0.49
LDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)	111.6 \pm 39.2	123.8 \pm 30.6	0.16
HDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)	42.9 \pm 10.0	45.9 \pm 9.6	0.21
WBC ($\times 10^9$ /L)	5.99 \pm 7.2	5.62 \pm 6.50	0.10
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	14.9 \pm 1.0	14.2 \pm 1.5	0.23
Platelet count ($\times 10^9$ /L)	191.9 \pm 40.2	225.6 \pm 32.0	0.06
MPV (fL)	8.02 \pm 0.72	7.50 \pm 0.32	<0.001
PDW	15.1 \pm 1.3	15.2 \pm 1.6	0.10

Abbreviations: M/F, male to female; BMI, body mass index; SBP-systolic blood pressure; DBP-diastolic blood pressure; LDL-cholesterol-low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; HDL-cholesterol-high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; WBC-white blood cell; MPV-mean platelet volume; PDW-platelet distribution width.

^aP value is for comparison between control and study population.

The values of platelet indices per months (30 days) up to 3 months of smoking cessation in participants who succeeded to quit smoking are given in Table 2.

Table2: Platelet Indices per 30 days-upto 3 Months of Smoking Cessation.

	Control n=25	Smoker n=46	1 months	2 months	3 months	P Value
Platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$)	225.6 \pm 32.0	191.9 \pm 40.2	196.8 \pm 39.3	206.4 \pm 36.7	223.8 \pm 39.8	<0.001
MPV (fL)	7.50 \pm 0.32	8.02 \pm 0.72	7.80 \pm 0.62	7.74 \pm 0.60	7.62 \pm 0.58	<0.001

Abbreviations: WBC-white blood cell; MPV-mean platelet volume.

P value is for comparison between control and study population overall.

Discussion:

The current study demonstrated that MPV was considerably greater in patients with smokers than in the control group. Thrombosis may develop due to endothelial injury, abnormal fibrinolysis, procoagulant activation and platelet abnormalities [35-38].

Increase in MPV was also seen in cardiovascular risk factors including smoking, diabetes mellitus, hypertension and hypercholesterolemia [39-41]. Higher MPV levels have been identified as an independent risk factor for death or recurrent vascular events after MI and coronary artery disease.[42] In the current study, smokers' platelet count was not substantially lower than the control group. The mechanism proposed for increased platelet activation in smokers is most likely because atherosclerosis and vascular endothelial dysfunction cause platelet activation, which leads to local thrombosis and inflammation. [43] Previous studies have demonstrated that prolonged smoking induces platelet activation [44-50]. Smoking cessation has also been demonstrated to increase platelet function. [45, 51]. The MPV is a basic and straightforward measure for evaluating platelet function.

In conclusion, we have found that the MPV values were significantly higher in smokers than those of controls. After 3 months of smoking cessation, MPV readings reduced considerably. Our findings may provide light on the pathophysiology of smoking cessation

and its positive impact on cardiovascular health. Our findings may increase the motivation for smokers to stop.

Our study indicated that habitual smokers had reduced platelet counts compared to controls. The MPV negatively correlates with total platelet count, perhaps indicating consumption of tiny platelets and compensatory creation of bigger reticulated platelets. As a result, restoration of endothelial function and/or decrease in oxidative stress may possibly improve platelet function within months after smoking cessation. The present study has some study limitations. Smoking status was monitored from self-reports given by participants.

It's important to note that smoking cessation is highly recommended to reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases associated with tobacco smoke. Quitting smoking can help improve endothelial function, reduce platelet activation, and decrease the overall risk of cardiovascular events. Additionally, adopting a healthy lifestyle, including regular exercise, a balanced diet, and avoiding secondhand smoke exposure, can further protect against cardiovascular diseases.

It's important to note that quitting smoking is challenging, and individuals may require support and resources to successfully quit. Healthcare professionals, counseling services, and smoking cessation programs can provide guidance, strategies, and treatments to assist smokers in their journey towards quitting.

By emphasizing the connection between smoking, platelet activation, and cardiovascular diseases, can contribute to increasing the motivation for smokers to make the decision to quit and ultimately improve their overall health and well-being.

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